

EFFECT OF THE SURFACE TREATMENT ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTY AND MORPHOLOGY OF CARBON FIBER

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to study the effect of surface treatment on the property and morphology of PAN based and pitch based carbon fibers. The variation of the surface characteristic of carbon fibers treated by nitric acid is investigated.

Single filament tests were performed to investigate the tensile strengths of the treated and untreated carbon fibers. Results obtained were analyzed by the Weibull distribution function. After surface modification, the PAN based high strength carbon fibers exist a higher and broader distribution in tensile strength, and the PAN based high modulus and pitch based carbon fibers show a fluctuation behavior in tensile strength. Surface morphology of the treated fiber were examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and fragments peel form fiber surface was observed for all three types of carbon fiber.

I. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers have been used in composite materials during the past decades. The efficiency of reinforcing depends on the adhesion between fibers and matrix⁽¹⁾. The studies of surface treatment were conducted to improve the mechanical properties of the composites⁽²⁾. The goal can be achieved by increasing the contact area and the affinity between matrix and fibers^(3,4). In general, dry gaseous oxidation⁽¹⁻⁴⁾, wet oxidation⁽⁴⁻⁷⁾, electrolytic oxidation⁽⁸⁻¹⁰⁾, and plasma treatment^(11,12) have commonly been used to treat the fiber surface. In this study, the nitric acid was employed to modify the surface of carbon fibers. The parameters of oxidation treatment and its effects on the tensile strength and the distribution of fiber strength are investigated, in addition, the surface morphology of the treated carbon fibers is also examined.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

The carbon fibers studied in this work involve PAN based high strength carbon fibers (HTA-7, 12K, Toho Rayon Co., Japan), high modulus carbon fibers (EHMS, 12K, Courtaulds Grafil Co. Ltd. U.K.), and pitch based carbon fibers (Dialead K32104, Mitsubisni Co., Japan). The sizing agent coated on the carbon fibers were removed in advance by reflux extracting with chloroform in a Soxhlet's extractor for five days, and then were washed with deionized water for two days. The fibers were then placed in a vaccum oven at 120°C for two days. After completing the above procedures, the naked carbon fibers were oxidized by 35 % HNO₃ at 50°C for 15, 30, 60, 150, 300, 600 minutes. The oxidation treated fibers were then washed with deionized water again for two days and were dried in a vacuum oven at 120 °C for two days.

After surface treatments, the tensile strength of the carbon filament was tested according to ASTM D3379-75 specification. The load cell of 100g was applied in this study. The crosshead speed was 0.5mm/min.

According to the suggestion in Referense⁽¹³⁾. The probability distribution function given in Eq.1 is adopted to analyze the tensile strength of carbon filament

$$F(x) = \int \left[\frac{\beta}{\theta - x_0} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{\theta - x_0} \right)^{\beta-1} \right] \left\{ \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x - x_0}{\theta - x_0} \right)^{\beta} \right] \right\} dx \quad (1)$$

where $F(x)$ is the strength distribution function, θ is the scale parameter, β is the shape parameter, x_0 is the expected minimum value of x and is also referred to as the location parameter, and x is the tensile strength of the single filament.

III. RESULTS AND DISSUSSION

III.1. Tensile Strength

The tensile strength of carbon fibers after treatments are summarized in Table.1. It is found that the average strength of carbon fibers which undergo surface treatment is higher than that without treatment for PAN based high strength(HS) carbon fiber. On the other hand, a significant improvement in average strength of the PAN based high modulus (HM) carbon fiber was observed after surface treatment for 300 minutes. For the pitch based carbon fiber, the variation in average strength shows a fluctuation behavior.

II.2. Weibull analysis

The Weibull distribution function which shown in Equation 1 was employed to calculate the shape parameter β . Figure 1 shows the Weibull probability distribution in average strength for the untreated and the treated PAN based HS carbon fiber. It was found that the

longer the treatment period, the broader the strength distribution will be. For the PAN based HM carbon fiber, however, the Weibull distribution of the average strength shows a different behavior. Figure 2 depicts the Weibull distribution of the average strength for HM fibers, a highest and narrowest distribution in strength was observed when the fibers was treated for 300 minutes. The Weibull distribution of strength for the pitch based carbon fiber was shown in Figure 3. A periodical variation in shape parameter is observed.

III.3. Morphology

According to the literature and the informations supplied by factory, the PAN based HS carbon fibers contain 95% carbon when treated at 1000°C⁽¹⁴⁾. The impurities (other than carbon, such as N and O) on the surface of the carbon fiber react with nitric acid, as a results, the etches on the fiber surface become significant. It is probably the reason why the distribution in strength of the fibers gets broader after surface treatment. Figure 4a shows the sizing of the original commerical available carbon fiber, the surface morphology after surface treatment for 60 and 600 minutes were depicted in Figure 4b and 4c respectively. After surface treatment for 60 minutes by nitric acid, the morphology on fiber surface shows a laminar peel-off phenomena; this result was predicted by the researchers in References 15,16 and 17. Once the treatment period increased, the outer layer which expose on the oxidation environment would peeled off, thus the surface morphology becomes rough and complicate and the distribution of strength gets broader.

For PAN based HM carbon fibers which are heat treated at 2800°C during fabrication process, a near 100% carbon content with a relatively perfect structure is reported¹⁴. The flaws on the fiber surface due to the existance of the metal particles and the flaws on the intersection between two adjacent layers extent after nitric acid treatment. Since the PAN based HM carbon fibers poss a more complete and order structure, reaction between the fibers and nitric acid is differ from that in PAN based HS carbon fiber. Figure 5 shows the surface morphology of HM carbon fiber after various periods of surface treatment. The existance of grooves on fiber surface was observed as received, the grooves get deeper when the treatment period was increased. Figure 5c shows that some fragments of the outest layer were removed after 300 minutes surface treatment. The surface morphology of the pitch based carbon fiber after treatment for various periods was similar to that of the PAN based carbon fiber. Figure 6 show the surface morphology of the pitch based carbon fiber after subjecting different periods of surface treatment in nitric acid. Although the grooves on the pitch based fiber surface is not significant, the laminar peel-off phenomenon was similar to that of the PAN based HM carbon fibers.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The average tensile strength of PAN based carbon fibers that undergo surface treatment is higher than that the untreated carbon fiber, however, these treated carbon fibers exhibit broader distribution in strength. For the PAN based high modulus carbon fibers, a significant improvement in average strength is observed when the fibers was subjected a surface treatment by nitric acid for 300 minutes. For pitch based carbon fiber, the change

in average strength shows a fluctuation variation.

For the PAN based high strength carbon fiber, when the treatment time increased, the outer layer would be peeled off randomly. Since the PAN based carbon fibers poss a more complete and order structure than that of the PAN based HS fibers, therefore the tensile strength after nitric acid treatment is differ. If the treatment parameters could be controlled properly, an enhancement in tensile strength of the PAN based high modulus carbon fiber and the pitch based carbon fiber is expected.

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VI. References

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Table.1 The tensile strength and shape parameter of different type carbon fiber treated with 35 % nitric acid at 50°C for various treated times

	PAN-based high strength	PAN-based high modulus	Pitch based
	Shape parameter	Tensile strength(GPa)	Shape parameter
Untreated	7.134	3.394	6.080
15 min	4.680	3.851	5.675
30 min	5.120	3.473	4.336
60 min	3.550	3.703	6.647
150 min	4.339	3.972	4.110
300 min	4.408	3.761	3.092
600 min	4.352	3.435	2.883

Figure.1. Weibull probability density distribution function-various tensile strength of PAN based high strength (HS) carbon fiber for different treated times.

Figure.2. Weibull probability density distribution function-various tensile strength of PAN based high modulus(HM) carbon fiber for different treated times.

Figure.3. Weibull probability density distribution function-various tensile strength of pitch based carbon fiber for different treated times.

(a)as-received

(a)15 min

(b) 60min

(b)60 min

(c) 600 min

(c) 300 min

Figure.4. SEM photographs of PAN based high strength (HS) carbon fiber surface treated by nitric acid by 35 % 50°C for various time. (a)as-received(b)60min.(c)600min.

Figure.5. SEM photographs of PAN based high modulus(HM) carbon fiber surface treated by nitric acid at 35 % 50°C for various time. (a)15min (b) 60min (c)300min

(a) 30 min

(b) 60 min

(c) 600 min

Figure 6. SEM photographs of pitch based carbon fiber surface treated with nitric acid at 35% 50 °C for various times. (a) 30 min. (b) 60 min. (c) 600 min.